

The First Resolution Revolution in Protein Structure Analysis: X-ray Diffraction of Polypeptide Conformations and Globular Protein Folds in 1950s and 1960s

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Abstract

Although determination of structures of biological molecules became a real possibility after the first X-ray analyses of crystals by the William Henry Bragg and his son Lawrence in 1913, the crystal structure determination of globular proteins became a possibility only in 1934 with the demonstration of X-ray diffraction from pepsin by J D Bernal and Dorothy Crowfoot, later Hodgkin, who had realised the importance of maintaining an aqueous environment for proteins in crystals. After a further 20 years of hard work by Max Perutz, John Kendrew and others the structures of haemoglobin and myoglobin emerged. Further innovation resulted in a revolution in X-ray diffraction studies in the 1960s, which focused first on polypeptides with alpha helix, beta strand and collagen polyproline helix structures, described in a review by David Davies in 1965 in the journal *Progress in Biophysics*, later to become *Progress in Biophysics and Molecular Biology*. It was followed in 1969 by a further detailed review by Tony North and David Phillips in the same journal on crystal structure analyses of globular proteins that successfully emerged soon after that of myoglobin. These included the structure of the first enzyme, lysozyme, followed by structures of chymotrypsin, trypsin, carboxypeptidase and many others. This first resolution revolution in X-ray analysis described in the two reviews is the subject of this retrospective analysis just over five decades later.

Introduction

In the 1950s impressive advances in understanding structures of both fibrous polypeptides and globular proteins occurred in parallel to the prediction of the structure of the DNA double helix. Together they revolutionised thinking about biological function at the molecular level. These advances in the 1950s and further developments in the early 1960s in understanding

polypeptide and protein structures were described in the journal *Progress in Biophysics*, the name of which later morphed to *Progress in Biophysics and Molecular Biology*. The first review was written at NIH in USA in 1965 by David Davies (Davies, 1965), who had previously worked in Cambridge on X-ray diffraction studies of polypeptide conformations, and the second in London by Tony North and David Phillips in 1969 (North & Phillips, 1969), who had defined the first structure of an enzyme, lysozyme, at the Royal Institution in 1965, and then in 1967 moved to Oxford to work on X-ray studies of crystalline proteins. These papers were published during the time that I was in Oxford doing my PhD and post-doctoral research, first in the laboratory of HM “Tiny Powell” and then with Dorothy Hodgkin. The two publications, which are the focus of this review, were very helpful to those of us using X-ray crystallography to define the structures of proteins in the 1960s and 70s.

As described in the two historic reviews (Davies, 1965; North & Phillips, 1969), research on polypeptides had a direct lineage from the first analyses of crystal structures in 1913 using X-rays by William Henry Bragg and his son Lawrence Bragg, to whom the Nobel prize was awarded two years later in 1915. J D Bernal, Figure 1A, generally known as “Sage”, one of the most important researchers to develop X-ray protein crystallography, began research with William Henry Bragg in the Davy Faraday Laboratory at the Royal Institution in London in 1922. In 1927, Bernal was appointed as the first lecturer in Structural Crystallography at Cambridge and became assistant director of the Cavendish Laboratory. He began work on complex biological molecules, recruiting two key figures in the history of protein X-ray crystallography. The first, Dorothy Crowfoot (Figure 1A), later Hodgkin, who left Oxford to work in Cambridge with Bernal in 1932, where she became involved in the first X-ray crystallographic studies of a protein, pepsin, before moving back to Oxford to start work on insulin in 1934. The second, Max Perutz, (Figure 1B) arrived from Austria in 1936, at a time when J.D. Bernal was looking for a research student to assist him with X-ray crystallography at the Cavendish Laboratory. Bernal encouraged him to focus on the use of X-ray diffraction to study the structure of proteins and Perutz began working on horse haemoglobin crystals for his PhD, with the first structures emerging 20 years later! In 1955 Lawrence Bragg had moved to the Royal Institution in London, recruiting David Phillips who begun work on lysozyme. Thus, the visions of the Braggs and Bernal concerning X-ray diffraction led to studies in Cambridge by Perutz, Oxford by Crowfoot Hodgkin and London by Phillips. Their research eventually led to structures of both fibrous polypeptides and globular proteins in the 1950s and 1960s, the focus of this review.

Figure 1: A. JD Bernal and Dorothy Crowfoot (Hodgkin) in 1934, B. John Kendrew and Max Perutz in 1962

The review of David Davies (Figure 2A; Davies, 1965) recounts the impressive developments, starting in the 1950's, concerning the prediction and experimental confirmation using X-rays of protein secondary structures for fibrous proteins including the alpha helix, beta strand and collagen polyproline helix. The emerging X-ray data on the three-dimensional structure of the myoglobin by Kendrew (Figure 1B; Kendrew et al., 1960) gave authors confidence that these results would be relevant to globular proteins. The review of Tony North and David Phillips (North & Phillips, 1969) takes the story forward as methods were further refined and developed to use isomorphous replacement and anomalous scattering in the definition of three-dimensional structures of proteins focussing on those structures that had already been studied in the mid-1960's.

Figure 2. David Davies, David Phillips

Here I discuss the advances in protein structures defined by X-ray crystallography described in the two papers. The articles had major impacts on the development of what is now known as structural biology, particularly for those of us who began working on protein structure during this time of revolutionary advance in the 1960s.

David Davies and his paper on X-ray Diffraction Studies of Polypeptide Conformations

David R. Davies was born in Wales in 1927 and between 1945 and 1952 studied physical chemistry in Magdalen College, Oxford, both as undergraduate and a postgraduate. After this he worked for two years as a post-doc at Caltech with Linus Pauling focusing on structures of molecules such as parabanic acid, a human metabolite an imidazolidine with substituted oxo-groups at positions 2, 4 and 5 (Davies and Blum, 1955). These structures used the first three-dimensional X-ray data sets together with the recently available computers for refinement of the structures. They provided further information on the geometry of amino acids, supporting Pauling's earlier structures proposed for the α -helix and β -sheet. From 1955, after moving to NIH, Bethesda, David Davies worked on oligonucleotides of DNA, the structure of the DNA triple helix, and structure factor calculations for some helical polypeptide models (Davies and Rich, 1959).

During two visits to the MRC Laboratory of Molecular Biology Cambridge UK in 1959 and 1963-1964, David Davies was a participant in John Kendrew's group that determined the crystal structure of myoglobin, the first high-resolution analysis of any protein (Kendrew et al., 1960). Between 1961 and 2012 he was Chief, Section on Molecular Structure, Lab of Molecular Biology, National Institutes of Diabetes, Digestive and Kidney Diseases, NIH, Bethesda, MD. During the 1970s he worked on a family of fungal enzymes related to pepsin, known as acid proteases derived from *Rhizopus chinensis* and *Endothia parasitica*, where I had the pleasure of collaborating with him (Subramanian et al., 1977)

This review by David Davies (1965) described the exciting developments in understanding the structures of the alpha helix by Pauling, Corey and Branson (1951), followed in the same year by the first development of a model for the beta-pleated-sheet structure by Pauling and Corey (1951b), and then a few years later the structure of the third important conformational class, the structure of collagen by Rich and Crick (1955). The modelled structures were developed by the careful study of conformations that were possible for polypeptides, in which the peptide moiety was kept planar and the internal hydrogen bonds were maximised. The model was further developed by Cochran, Crick and Vand (1952) by comparing the predicted and the observed X-ray in diffraction intensities. This approach revolutionised the interpretation of fibrous structures in the 1950s, but the review by David Davies focusses mainly on the developments that occurred a decade later. These were influenced by the then recent determination at 2 Å resolution of the three-dimensional structure of sperm-whale myoglobin (Kendrew *et al.*, 1960, 1961), which provided proof of the arrangement, predicted earlier, of

these helices, for example Figure 3,. The myoglobin structure is of course remarkable in having 150 amino acids, of which 118 are located in α -helices in 8 segments, ranging from 7 to 24 residues. David Davies pointed out that one of the helices is bent and he discusses how this might result from individual site interactions in the globular protein. He emphasised the fact the α -helix is not an entirely rigid structure but may become distorted to accommodate the local packing.

Figure 3. Stereogram of the E-helix of myoglobin (Kendrew et al., 1960), reproduced from Davies (1965).

David Davies also updated the then current understanding of α -keratin, for which many papers in the early 1950's had predicted some form of α -helical coiled coil (Crick, 1952; Pauling and Corey, 1953). Crick and others used a “knobs into holes” packing of the side chains, stimulating the development of an understanding of X-ray scattering by coils by Crick in 1953 (Crick 1953). The interest in α -keratin was that chains with a large number of alanine, leucine, arginine and cysteine residues, which prefer alpha helical conformations, can pack together in pairs to form left-handed helical structure coiled-coil. Furthermore, these coiled-coil dimers could be bonded with disulphide bonds using cysteine residues, many of which are found in α -keratins. This review of David Davies in Progress, therefore, brought up to date the predicted structures. Davies also commented on the work of Cohen and Holmes (Cohen and Holmes, 1963), who had published just before his own review, greatly improved X-ray diffraction patterns of muscles, concluding that the two-stranded model was better than that with three strands.

David Davies (1965) discussed the parallel development in understanding the β -conformation of polypeptide chains. These extended polypeptides have a 2-fold screw axis along the chain

with a repeat of between 6.5 and 7 Å resolution. As is now well understood this is usually stabilised by formation of hydrogen bonds between the NH groups of one chain and the CO groups of another. Impressively, Pauling and Corey (1953) realised that both parallel and anti-parallel pleated sheets could exist. Marsh and colleagues (Marsh *et al*, 1955 a, b) showed that the anti-parallel chain structures proposed to account for the cross-beta pattern of the egg stalk of the green lace-wing fly (Figure 4), in the silk fibroin of the *Bombyx mori* silk worm as well as in Tussah silk worms which provide natural fibres used in many clothes and soft furnishing, for example in cushions.

Figure 4. The Chinese Cracker structure, proposed to account for the cross-beta pattern of the egg stalk of the green lace-wing fly, reproduced from Davies (1965). The arrow gives the direction of the fibre axis, and the dotted lines represent hydrogen bonds.

For the *Bombyx mori* structure it was assumed that every other residue in the polypeptide was glycine, leading to a surface that would allow two sheets to pack. David Davies pointed out that there were, on the basis of their X-ray patterns, a variety of silks, where repeats of different lengths related to the presence of bulkier side-chains including arginine, glutamic acid and tyrosine. Davies also reviewed the observation made by Fraser MacRae (1962) that β -keratins obtained by stretching α -fibres gave longer fibres with an anti-parallel pleated sheet structure and he went on to describe other cross- β diffraction patterns that had been identified in the early 1960s, advancing subject in an impressive way.

David Davies also reviewed advances in the structure of collagen, where by 1953 many structures had been proposed by Astbury *et al.* (1940), Pauling and Corey (1951) and Corey *et al.* (1953). A major advance in 1954, using X-ray analysis and published in *Nature* by the impressive Indian duo G.N. Ramachandran and G Kartha (Ramachandran and Kartha, 1954) proposed a structure that anticipated the conformations with a 3-fold screw axis, in which three chains slowly coiled around a common axis in a right-handed direction thus forming a coiled-coil. This was a remarkable example of the very thoughtful work coming out of India, independent of other work in Cambridge, UK. However, criticism from Rich and Crick (1955), concerned short contacts and incompatibility of the proposed structure with a sequence of Gly-Arg-Pro. Rich and Crick concluded that no structure with two systematic sets of hydrogen bonds was satisfactory stereochemically and therefore they proposed two structures, each having one hydrogen bond per three amino acids based on the structure of polyglycine II. Interestingly a similar conclusion reached by Cowan-McGavin and North (1955), the same Tony North who features in the second review on globular proteins, discussed below. Having

reviewed the polyproline II structure, Ramachandran agreed with the need to avoid the short contacts, and the structures were published by Rich and Crick (1961). David Davies in his review in Progress describes a symposium on collagen in Madras in 1960 where the debate about the structure with two hydrogen bonds was re-opened by Ramachandran and colleagues (Figures 5A and 5B: Ramachandran, Sasisekharan and Thathachari, 1962; Lakshmanan, Ramakrishnan, Sasisekharan and Thathachari, 1962; Ramachandran et al., 1963). The helix dimensions were modified to 2.95 Å for the height per three-residue unit and from 3.33 to 3.28 for the number of units per turn. This also led to a debate about expected distances and generally accepted van der Waals radii at the time of the Davies paper, although there still had been an ongoing discussion about the two models that depended on the interpretation of the diffraction pattern of the un-stretched molecule of collagen.

A.

Figure 5. A: The fully allowed (continuous line) and outer limit (dashed line) of main chain dihedral angles described by Ramachandran et al. (1963) with additional data for 3_{10} -helix, taken from work by Schellman and Schellman (1964), reproduced from Davies (1965). B: The evolved Ramachandran plot showing torsional angles: ϕ (ϕ) is the $C(i-1), N(i), Ca(i), C(i)$ torsion angle and ψ (ψ) is the $N(i), Ca(i), C(i), N(i+1)$ torsion angle for amino acids in the lysozyme X-ray structure. Figure reproduced from North and Phillips (1969)

The Russian group involving Drs Natalia S. Andreeva and Yuri Chirgadze also published work on collagen in 1963 (Andreeva et al., 1963). Both of these scientists moved to protein crystallography soon afterwards, and I was impressed by their contributions when I attended the 1966 International Congress of Crystallography in Moscow. Meeting them resulted in long-term friendships and collaborations in the following decades on aspartic proteinases, for example (Newman et al., 1991) and gamma-crystallins (Sergeev et al., 1987). At the time of my first meeting I was unaware of their contributions to the structure of collagen, which established how structures of interacting molecules with one hydrogen bond between the two could stabilise a collagen structure. Davies describes their proposal (Andreeva and Millionova, 1963) of an alternative structure, in which the polypeptide chain has 3-fold screw axis and is very similar to the model Ramachandran and Kartha. The consensus of information now is that the tropocollagen molecule has three left-handed procollagens that form a right-handed triple helical super structure.

Thus, this review by David Davies very thoughtfully emphasises the multinational nature of the discoveries concerning fibrous proteins. Many spent time in Oxford, Cambridge or London, and in the US with either Linus Pauling in Pasadena, California or with Davies in NIH. However, as described above, independent advances were made in Moscow by Andreeva & Chirgadze; and in Madras by Ramachandran and Kartha. Many of these groups used their experience to contribute to the later developments in defining globular protein structures using X-rays. The review also demonstrated how difficult it was to interpret unequivocally three-dimensional structures from X-ray fibre patterns, even with good assumptions about van der Waals interactions and hydrogen bond lengths. The emerging structures of globular proteins, especially Kendrew's myoglobin structure (Kendrew et al., 1960), provided reassuring information that the alpha helical structure proposed for keratin was reasonable.

However, the models of fibrous proteins also informed further early work on globular protein three-dimensional structures and the refinement of these structures. Many of those researchers involved in fibrous protein structure analyses moved on to study globular proteins. This part of the history of structural biology then links into the second review that I discuss here, published in *Progress in Biophysics and Molecular Biology X-ray Studies of Crystalline Proteins* (North & Phillips, 1969).

X-ray Studies of Crystalline Proteins

The review by A.C.T. North and D.C. Phillips (North & Phillips, 1969) appears to have been written around 1967, but published in 1969, fifteen years after a paper in *Progress in Biophysics* by John Kendrew (Kendrew J., 1954) had discussed the use of X-ray crystallography of crystalline proteins. In the same year, 1954, Perutz and colleagues (Green et al., 1954), working in the same laboratory in Cambridge, had demonstrated that isomorphous replacement might be used to determine the structures of crystalline proteins, without using what now would be called molecular replacement. However, the high-resolution structure of sperm-whale myoglobin did not appear until a few years later by Kendrew and colleagues in 1960 (Kendrew et al., 1960). The structure of oxyhaemoglobin at only low resolution had been analysed using the structure of myoglobin as a guide (Perutz et al., 1960).

Tony North and David Phillips describe how new protein structures began to emerge rather quickly in the mid-60s with the X-ray analysis of hen egg-white lysozyme in atomic detail (Figure 6) from their laboratory in 1965 (Blake et al., 1965) and then two years later structures of further proteins including ribonuclease-A (Kartha et al., 1967), ribonuclease-S (Wyckoff et al., 1967), alpha-chymotrypsin (Matthews et al., 1967), and carboxypeptidase A (Steitz et al., 1967; Reeke et al., 1967). The low resolution studies published in 1967 and included in the review of North and Phillips (1969), soon after reported at higher resolutions included papain (Drenth et al., 1967), carbonic anhydrase (Fridborg et al., 1967) and cytochrome-C (Dickerson

et., 1967). All of these structure analyses depended on multiple isomorphous replacement and anomalous scattering.

The authors of this review Tony North and David Phillips had by 1969 lived through a very exciting period of revolution and evolution of X-ray crystallography of proteins. David Phillips was the son of a master tailor and Methodist preacher. His mother was a midwife and her father Samuel Finney, a coal miner union official and Member of Parliament, the latter of which I realised when I was elected as a Labour Councillor in the City of Oxford and David Phillips gave me his support in this endeavour. Although he was born in Ellesmere, Shropshire, after education at the local High School for Boys, David moved to University College of South Wales, where he began to study physics, electrical engineering, and mathematics. In 1944, before completing his degree, he was called for service in the Royal Navy as a radar officer, but returned to Cardiff to complete his degree in 1948. He then stayed on for his PhD, completed in 1951, to work on alkaloids and other organic substances with Arthur Wilson, a lecturer in the Department of Physics at University College, Cardiff, who later became Professor of Physics. After a postdoctoral at the National Research Council in Ottawa, David Phillips joined the Royal Institution. I first got to know him in 1966 when he became Professor of Molecular Biophysics in the Department of Zoology at the University of Oxford and the Dorothy Hodgkin protein group, then working in the Department of Crystallography, where I was a member working on insulin, joined him in 1967. Apart from gaining many prizes and distinctions, including the Feldberg Prize 1968, Sir Hans Krebs Medal 1971, Knight Bachelor 1979 and membership of the House of Lords, he became a Fellow of the Royal Society and its Biological Secretary from 1976 to 1983, and later Chief Scientific Advisor to the UK Government.

David Phillips' most significant contribution scientifically was the structure of lysozyme in 1965 at the Royal Institution, where one of his senior colleagues was Anthony C. T. (Tony) North. Tony also had a first degree in Physics, followed by a PhD at King's College, London for X-ray fibre diffraction studies of the protein collagen (see above; Cowan-McGavin and North, 1955). He then spent 11 years with Sir Lawrence Bragg at the Royal Institution, first collaborating with Max Perutz in determining the 3-dimensional structure of haemoglobin (Perutz et al., 1960) and then with David Phillips and on the 3-dimensional structure and mechanism of action of hen egg-white lysozyme, which was the first enzyme to be solved at atomic resolution (Blake et al., 1965). Tony North's contribution was mainly in developing the computer software for automated data collection and analysis. Indeed lysozyme was the first protein crystallographic analysis carried out entirely by computer. He then moved with David Phillips to Oxford in 1966, focusing on the molecular replacement method using known structure homologues to solve the phase problem. In Leeds from 1972 as Astbury Professor of Biophysics he continued the development of computer graphics both for crystallographic work and for drug discovery for pharmaceutical use.

North and Phillips (1969) discuss the challenges that were recognised in X-ray protein crystallography including the resolution and the quality of the phase determination. It reviews the challenges, which had been met fully at the time of writing in 1967, two years before publication, only in myoglobin and lysozyme. Of course it also became evident that

once a protein had been defined for one homologue, others could be modelled and this was demonstrated by North, Phillips and colleagues for lactalbumin, based on the structure of lysozyme (Browne, 1969). The roles of small molecules, either as co-factors or substrate/inhibitors, and the use of X-ray methods to define the structures and infer evidence about mechanisms of enzymes and other proteins, were obviously a major focus of an important paper by Louise Johnson and David Phillips (Johnson and Phillips, 1965). The review of North and Phillips (1969), discussed here, therefore focused on the huge development of successful structure analyses in the years of the mid 1960's.

A major section of the North and Phillips (1969) review deals with solubility of proteins. Crystals were generally mounted inside a quartz or glass capillary alongside a reservoir of the solvent used for the crystallisation. Various kinds of flow cells were developed and these were discussed in this review but to my knowledge not very widely used. The review also discusses other work mainly developing from the laboratory of Fred Richards (Bishop, Quioco and Richards, 1966) of using cross-links with glutaraldehyde, discussing the fact that cross linking certainly can lead to some disorder in hen egg-white lysozyme tetragonal crystals, although other forms of lysozyme were not disordered.

A second focus of the review was the preparation of isomorphous heavy atom derivatives, with a major emphasis on covalent derivatives, which had been pioneered by Perutz (Green, Ingram and Perutz, 1954) using 4-chloromercuribenzoic acid (p-chloromercuribenzoic acid, PCMB) which reacts with thiol groups in a protein. A further systematic approach was the substitution of metals in metalloproteins, for example substitution of zinc with mercury ions. They also discussed trial and error derivatives, which certainly became widely used in protein crystallography in the longer term, for example with platinum complexes PtCl_4^{2-} . However, there was very little analysis of the probability of metal ions binding sidechain groups such as carboxylates of glutamic or aspartic acids or imidazoles of histidines. In fact many of these approaches were being exploited in the adjacent lab with the challenging insulin structure where agents that replace zinc and bind histidine or those like lead or uranyl, which were being developed as part of the Hodgkin group insulin analysis (Blundell et al., 1969) The North and Phillips (1969) review also looked at the challenges in the mid-1960's of measuring X-ray diffraction intensities that varied as radiation damaged crystals. Although Weissenberg and oscillation photographs as well as computer controlled X-ray diffractometers were developed in the 1960's.

Another theme of the review was the emerging realisation that anomalous scattering could be helpful, particularly that from the heavy atoms of the isomorphous derivatives. This was first used in the study of proteins by Blow and was heavily exploited in the insulin work of the Hodgkin group using lead or uranyl heavy atoms and new software developed by Eleanor Dodson. This had been suggested by Singh and Ramaseshan (1966). North and Phillips also consider the use of anomalous scattering measurements by using a Patterson function with coefficients with anomalous scattering differences between Bijvoet pairs of reflections from the same crystals. This synthesis features peaks corresponding to the vectors between atoms that are scattering anomalously, as pointed out by Rossmann (1961). This method required very precise measurements of the intensity differences due to anomalous scattering, intensity differences are small, and the idea was discussed widely in many centres, including by Kartha

and Parthasarathy (1965), Matthews (1966) and Singh and Ramaseshan (1966). This approach had a huge impact on insulin where we produced lead and uranyl derivatives that had strong anomalous scattering. The Hodgkin group contributions that were developed in parallel to the writing of the article by North and Phillips (1969) article used uranyl derivatives that allowed very good phasing but when combined with a corrected interpretation of the lead derivative allowed the structure of insulin to be solved (Blundell et al., 1969).

North and Phillips also discuss the use of direct methods, defined as methods for determining protein structures that do not depend on the preparation of a series of isomorphous derivatives. Of course there was in parallel extensive analyses of such approaches for small molecules but the methods clearly had limitations as the number of atoms increased. One of the fascinating aspects of the subject was the use of the tangent formula of Karle and Hauptman (1956), which is used to generate phases from a set of starting phases. However, all of these approaches, which have the same assumptions as direct methods, require that the electron density is positive, that the structure is resolved into equal atoms and the structures have only a few atoms, less than 100. My own experience with the tangent formula in trying to improve the insulin maps in 1967 was that consecutive cycles of the tangent formula refinement indicated a clearing up and sharpening of the maps accompanied by an improvement of the phases in the first cycle but subsequent cycles caused electron density to pile up in places corresponding to large electron density peaks in the original map (Blundell & Johnson, 1976). Later experiments by Hendrickson and Karle (1973) showed that the tangent formula might be useful for resolutions better than 2 Å.

Figure 6: Stereo photographs of an atomic model of the hen egg-white lysozyme molecule. Figure reproduced from North and Phillips (1969).

The paper then had a very thoughtful discussion of “image” focusing on the resolution which largely depends on the minimum interplanar spacing for the structure factor aptitudes that are included in the analyses. A major feature of this of course was the number of reflections that had to be measured. For example, at 5.0 Å resolution for lysozyme work of North and Phillips, there were 623 reflections but at 2 Å resolution the figure would be increased to 8542. This emphasised the fact that at higher resolutions the number of reflections increases sharply. All of these were challenges while the data collection methods were in the early days not automated.

The North and Phillips paper had extensive discussion of the various attempts to interpret images at these different resolutions in the development of protein crystallography in the 1950's and 1960's. In many ways the structures of myoglobin with 70% of the structure as alpha helices provided a more helpful analysis than Perutz's earlier work looking at the homologue haemoglobin at lower resolution or the work on lysozyme where the alpha helix was less prevalent. The review of North and Phillips has very interesting and helpful analyses of the resolution challenge, in particular, the identification of side-chains and all main-chain carbonyl groups which allow the conformation at lower resolutions to be interpreted, especially in the earlier work of Kendrew and Perutz. Clearly the aromatic side-chain (histidine, tryptophan, tyrosine, phenylalanine) can be recognised with these and used to define the sequence alignment with the electron density. However, in subsequent studies of very much larger proteins even at moderate resolutions, for example our own work in the last decade on the giant protein kinase DNA-PKcs with over 4000 amino acids in a single chain have proved a major challenge at 4.3 Å (Blundell and Chaplin, 2021), and such analyses continue to be critically important in larger systems where the resolution is less good.

The North and Phillips review discusses the challenges of refinement mentioning the work of Diamond (1966) which included a computer model building programme designed to fit groups of atoms with standard steroid chemistry to a list of coordinates from a model. Such computational approaches began to dominate at this period to improve the analyses of the lower resolution electron density maps. The review then discusses the relevant advantages of the real and reciprocal approaches that we used in many methods focussing finally and defining the most promising approach to lie with Diamond formulation of molecular geometry that can be used to relate changes in the dihedral angles to changes in calculated structure factors. This was tried out with myoglobin and lysozyme but also used quite extensively on insulin in close collaborations between our group and that of Diamond's group that was based in the Computing Laboratory, not so distant from the Hodgkin group in Oxford.

The paper discusses the results on low and high resolution structures of beginning of course with the haem proteins and discussing the relationship of the structures to the allowed regions predicted by Ramachandran et al. (1963) in the well-used “Ramachandran plot”, also discussed by Davies(1965) and shown in Figure 5b. North and Phillips point out that the first structures revealed a general distribution of side-chains as first observed in myoglobin (Figure 7).

Figure 7. Schematic diagram showing the conformation of the polypeptide chain in sperm-whale myoglobin and the environment of the haem group (Original figure from North and Phillips (1969), reproduced by permission of Dr. R. E. Dickerson).

However, this does not imply that all non-polar side-chains are varied within the molecules and all polar ones are exposed. Secondly, they show that the conformation of the molecules defined after myoglobin and haemoglobin show less importance of the alpha-helical conformation and increases of beta-structure. The paper concludes with the observation that in the ten years prior to the writing of this paper, roughly between 1957 and 1967, the challenges of data collection and computation evolved to be no longer daunting, at least for molecular weights up to 50,000.

Conclusion

Both reviews discussed here proved very useful as they were written at a time of major developments in structural biology using X-ray crystallography. For someone who was working on the structure of insulin finally published in 1969, the developments discussed by Davies North and Phillips allowed us to think and develop methodology. For insulin the major developments were in accurate data collection so that we could measure anomalous scattering in several derivatives that then allowed better phasing at high resolution.

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Declaration of interest

The author declares no conflict of interests.

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